

Meloidogyne graminicola and Sclerotium rolfsii interaction in rice

B.P. Hazarika, Department of Plant Pathology, Indian Council for Agricultural Research, (RC) Manipur Center, Imphal 795004, India

Rice root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne graminicola* causes yield losses of up to 18% in rainfed upland rice in eastern India, and seedling blight disease of rice, caused by *Sclerotium rolfsii*, is seen to be associated with it (Mathur 1973). This observation led to the investigation of the nature and type of association among rice cultivar IR8, *M. graminicola*, and *S. rolfsii*.

Samples of IR8 plants with an intact root system and rhizosphere soil collected from the 0–5-cm depth of a rainfed upland rice field served as a source of inoculum for the greenhouse experiments.

Earthen pots (15 × 15 cm) were used after rinsing the samples in 2% formaldehyde and air-drying for potting soil. Upland rice field soil (79 sand:16 silt:5 clay), with a pH of 5.0 from the top 16 cm, was steam-sterilized at 15 kg cm⁻² pressure and placed in pots at 1,000 g pot⁻¹. Seeds of IR8 were dehusked, soaked in 0.52% sodium hypochlorite for 1 h (Keobooneung 1971), and rinsed in distilled water thrice before sowing in 2% agar in 15 × 15-cm jars in an all-glass seed germination chamber. When seedlings reached the 3–4-leaf stage 18–23 d after sowing, they were planted at one seedling pot⁻¹. Water was always adjusted to

approximately 32% of soil moisture content.

Interaction was studied by introducing six treatments in six replications (see table). Based on earlier research (Rao and Israel 1972) on the rate of invasion and behavior of nematodes in roots, *M. graminicola* was inoculated at 100 larvae sprout⁻¹ at 3 d and at 500 larvae seedling⁻¹ at 15 d. An equal amount of soil and water or PDA without fungus was added with the nematode to simulate fungus inoculation. Ten grams of substrate containing spore and mycelium was diluted with 90 mL of distilled water to provide inocula at 1 mL 3-d-old seedling⁻¹ and 2.5 mL 15-d-old seedling⁻¹.

The prevalence of nematode and fungus was estimated from all treatments 30 d after the second inoculation, and plant growth characters were compared. The number of galls decreased significantly in the presence of the fungus, indicating the negative effect of the fungus on nematode development. The negative effect of fungal invasion was demonstrated by the reduced number of endoparasites (all stages) in treatments in which the fungus was inoculated first and the nematode a week later. In these treatments, the percentage

of males was highest and fungal development was best. Fresh weight of roots and tillers, shoot height, and dry weight decreased in nematode and fungus associations. Similar observations were reported by other researchers working with *M. javanica* and *Fusarium moniliforme* or maize variety Hybrid 17 A with *F. solani* or *Rhizoctonia solani*—the association decreased plant growth more significantly than did either the nematode or the fungus alone (Ibrahim and Rezk 1978).

All these factors indeed show an interaction between *M. graminicola* and *S. rolfsii* in rice. Roots invaded by *S. rolfsii* were not suitable for the development of *M. graminicola*.

References

- Ibrahim IKA, Rezk MA. 1978. Pathogenicity of *M. javanica* and certain fungi on corn. *Alex. J. Agric. Res.* 26(2):441–446.
- Keobooneung S. 1971. Effect of rice-root nematode *Hirschmanniella* (Van Breda de Hann 1902) Luc and Goodey 1963 on rice seedlings. PhD thesis, Louisiana State University, USA.
- Mathur SC. 1973. Studies on seedling blight of rice caused by *Sclerotium rolfsii*. *Riso* 22(3):231–237.
- Rao YS, Israel P. 1972. Influence of inoculum density on the final population of the rice root-knot nematode. *Indian J. Nematol.* 2:72–76.

Meloidogyne graminicola and Sclerotium rolfsii interaction in rice cv. IR8.

Treatment	Galls (no.)	Total endoparasites (all stages) (log 10 value)	% of males	Fungal development ^a (no.)	Tillers plant ⁻¹ (no.)	Shoot		Fresh root wt (g)
						Height (cm)	Dry wt (mg)	
T1 <i>M. graminicola</i> alone	263.4	3.68	38.8	–	1.8	39.4	617.0	4.81
T2 <i>S. rolfsii</i> alone	–	–	–	+	1.6	38.6	608.6	4.61
T3 T1 + T2 together	194.8	3.74	41.5	++	1.4	34.6	549.0	4.14
T4 T1 first and T2 a week later	189.7	3.41	40.5	+	1.3	30.2	399.2	4.14
T5 T2 first and T1 a week later	211.0	3.30	51.2	++	1.6	31.2	578.2	3.82
T6 Uninoculated	–	–	–	–	2.1	43.9	764.0	5.81
CD 0.0537.3	0.13			0.27	2.5	78.7	0.43	

^a+ = less, ++ = more, – = none.